

NOTES

Complex Formation of Au(III) with Chromotropic Acid

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CHROMOTROPIC acid (H_4A) figures prominently in the discussion of hydroxy carboxylic acids and provides two $-OH$ groups for coordination. This has attracted the attention of many workers to explore the interaction of this acid with many metal ions¹⁻³. A close examination of the existing literature reveals the absence of any study on Au(III)-chromotropic acid system.

Experimental

AnalaR (B.D.H) sodium hydroxide, gold chloride supplied by Johnson Mathey & Co., London and disodium salt of CTA (E. Merck) were used. A Cambridge pH meter was used to determine the H^+ concentration of the reaction mixtures.

Conductance measurements were carried out by a conductometer (WTW Leitfähigkeitsmesser, type IBR, made in Germany) with magic eye as a visual indicator.

The experimental procedure consisted of potentiometric and conductometric titrations of ligand in the absence and presence of gold chloride against standard alkali.

Results and Discussion

The appearance of inflection and breaks after the addition of one mole of alkali per mole of ligand (Fig. 1, Curve 1 & 1') correspond to the neutralisation of one of the phenolic $-OH$ groups of CTA. There is no inflection and break observed for the second $-OH$, because of hydrogen bond formation⁴. The reaction may be represented as

When ligand is mixed with Au(III) solution in 1 : 1 ratio, there is observed a considerable lowering in the pH, due to complex formation. This mixture when titrated against standard alkali gave two

Fig. 1. Potentiometric and Conductometric Titration Curves of CTA in the absence and presence of Au(III) with 0.1M NaOH—Curves 1 & 1', $3.3 \times 10^{-3}M$ CTA; Curves 2 & 2', $3.3 \times 10^{-3}M$ CTA + $3.3 \times 10^{-3}M$ Au(III); Curves 3 & 3', $6.6 \times 10^{-3}M$ CTA + $3.3 \times 10^{-3}M$ Au(III).

inflections at $m=1$ & $m=2$ (Curve 2, Fig.1). The first inflection corresponds to the neutralisation of $H(AuCl_3OH)$, the form in which aqueous solution of $AuCl_3$ exists⁵. The second inflection at $m=2$ corresponds to the formation of a complex ion $(AuACl_2)^{-3}$. The reactions may be represented as :

Titration of 2 : 1 mixture of ligand and Au(III) solution against standard alkali indicates two inflections at $m=1$ and $m=3$ (Curve 3, Fig. 1). The first corresponds to the neutralisation of $H(AuCl_3OH)$ and the second corresponds to the formation of complex ion $(AuACl_2)^{-3}$. Anion $(HA)^{-3}$ is not neutralised owing to H-bond formation as shown

in equation 1. The reactions may be represented as :

The formation of complex ion $(AuACl_2)^{-3}$ is further confirmed by conductometric titrations. The breaks at $m=1$ and $m=2$ in the 1 : 1 mixture and at $m=1$ and $m=3$ in 2 : 1 ligand—Au(III) solution mixture confirm the formation of complex as shown by equations given above.

The present investigation clearly reveals the formation of 1 : 1 complex in pH range 7-10.

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Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(III) Complexes of a Mixed Oxygen-Nitrogen Donor

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THE metal complexes of the tridentate O-N-N donors usually exhibit interesting magnetic, spectral and structural properties¹⁻³. The strategic disposition of the donor sites in many of such ligands forces the metal ions to dimerise or polymerise, leading to metal complexes where antiferromagnetic interaction becomes their special characteristic. In this preliminary communication, we report the ligational behaviour of benzoylhydrazone of biacetylmonoxime (LH₂) towards Co(III), Ni(II) and Cu(II) ions in both its keto and enol forms.

In an alcoholic medium of pH 4-5, the ligand behaves as a tridentate neutral donor and forms

1 : 1 type Cu(II) complexes. With Ni(II) only 1 : 2 type chelates have been isolated. In the case of the Co(III) complex, the initially used Co(II) salt is found to be oxidised to Co(III) and a complex of the formula $Co(LH)_3H_2O$ is isolated. In a medium of pH 6-8, where the enol-form predominates, neutral Co(III), Ni(II) and Cu(II) chelates, corresponding to a metal : ligand ratio of 1 : 1, have been synthesised in the case of Cu(II) and Ni(II) and 1 : 2 in the case of Co(III). The analytical data and room temperature magnetic moment values of the complexes are given in Table I. The room

TABLE I

Complex	Colour	Analysis %			μ_{eff} B.M. 300°K
		Metal	Nitrogen	Anion	
Co(LH) ₃ .H ₂ O	Orange	8.18 (8.31)	16.90 (17.08)	—	Dia- magnetic
Co(LH)(L)	Chocolate red	11.84 (11.92)	17.12 (17.00)	—	Dia- magnetic
Ni(LH ₂) ₂ .Cl ₂ . 2H ₂ O	Yellowish grey	9.58 (9.73)	13.80 (13.91)	11.80 (11.74)	2.98
Ni(LH ₂) ₂ .Br ₂ . 2H ₂ O	Greenish grey	8.55 (8.47)	11.98 (12.12)	22.97 (23.07)	3.00
Ni(LH ₂) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂ . 2H ₂ O	Pale yellow	9.00 (8.93)	16.95 (17.05)	—	2.91
Ni(L)	Brown red	21.16 (21.23)	15.14 (15.23)	—	Dia- magnetic
Cu(LH ₂)Cl ₂ . H ₂ O	Yellowish green	16.97 (17.10)	11.45 (11.30)	19.14 (19.00)	1.77
Cu(LH ₂)(NO ₃) ₂ . H ₂ O	Ultrama- rin blue	15.00 (14.96)	16.29 (16.48)	—	1.81
Cu(L)	Blackish green	22.51 (22.64)	15.00 (14.92)	—	1.00

* Figures in the parenthesis indicate the calculated values.

temperature magnetic moment of all the Cu(II) complexes of the keto form of the ligand lie within the range of 1.77-1.81 B.M. and is indicative of either a square-planar or a distorted octahedral stereochemistry⁴. For the Ni(II) complexes, the magnetic moment values lie in the range of 2.91-3.00 B.M. The Co(III) complexes of the keto and the enol forms of the ligand are diamagnetic. The Ni(II) complex of the enol form of the ligand is also diamagnetic ; whereas, the Cu(II) complex shows subnormal magnetic moment value (1.00 B.M.) at room temperature indicating a strong spin-spin interaction within this chelate molecule, probably existing in a dimeric state.

A comparison of the i.r. spectra of the ligand and the metal complexes in the keto form reveals that the broad band at 3320-3280 cm⁻¹, originally present in the ligand and assigned to the superimposed stretching vibrations of the -NH and the oxime -OH groups⁵, has not been distinguished ; instead, there appears a broad and unsymmetrical absorption band around 3500-3200 cm⁻¹, which might be due to the stretching vibration of the coordinated or lattice water molecules overlapping the -NH and -OH stretches. A striking modification observed is that, the band at 1640 cm⁻¹, assigned as